

**IMPACT OF LEVERAGING SECONDARY ASSOCIATIONS TO BUILD BRAND EQUITY
A CASE STUDY OF RELIANCE JIO****Shailendra C. Mishra***Assistant Professor, Mat. K.M. Patel Sr. College of Com. & Sci.***Abstract**

Brand name creates loyalty, trust, faith, premium-ness or mass market appeal depending on how the brand is marketed, advertised and promoted. People do not buy products but they buy brands. Successful organizations have the power of their brands as the cornerstone of their success. An important aspect of branding is brand equity. Every firm aims at building equity. In general, brand equity refers to the value of a brand. It is the consumer perception towards the brand. If the consumer has high degree of association with the brand, it leads to high level of brand equity. The final way to build brand equity is to leverage secondary associations. Brand associations may themselves be linked to other entities that have their own associations, creating these secondary associations. For example, the brand may be linked to certain source factors, such as the company, countries or other geographical regions and channels of distribution as well as to other brands, characters, people, sporting or cultural events. In this research paper, an attempt is made to find out the impact of leveraging secondary associations to build brand equity with the case of a successful brand Reliance Jio.

Keywords: Brand, Leverage, Secondary Association

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/amierj/>

Introduction

Leveraging of secondary brand associations or related brand associations is one of the ways of building brand equity. Brand may be linked with other entities, which have their own knowledge structure in the minds of the consumers. Secondary brand associations are important in creating strong, favourable and unique associations or responses if the existing associations are deficient. Some brand associations reflect the source factors while some are related to people, places and things. Brand Associations that are related to Source Factors:

- Company
- Country of Origin
- Channel of Distribution
- Co-branding
- Characters (through Licensing)
- Events

Leveraging of secondary brand associations leads to indifferent approach from customer towards brand. However, if consumers do not have knowledge of associating company than there could be no knowledge transfer and cannot

translate into benefit for the brand. Even if the consumers have brand knowledge how much relevance it holds for the current brand also has to be ascertained. If a company is to introduce a new brand the first step of association is with corporate brand if it exists. In this research paper we have focused on a brand named as Reliance JIO which is a telecommunication company.

Research Objectives

This research study was conducted with the following set of objectives:

- To understand the different secondary association which can be leveraged with new brand
- To study the effectiveness of secondary association on new brand
- To suggest some recommendation to new brands when they are planning to leverage secondary brand association.

Scope

- This case study will be helpful for any new emerging brand
- This study will facilitate a great scope to marketing students / trainees.

Research Methodology

The research design of the present study is descriptive in nature and crafted on the basis of the objectives and the nature of the problem to be explored, and the availability of time and the skill of the researcher. The data required for the present study was collected from secondary sources ie. from internet, newspaper, manuals etc.

Literature Review

The review literature shows that leveraging secondary association to new brands always makes it possible for that brand to be easily accepted by the customers. The Implementation of Leverage Secondary Association through Stakeholder Approach in Reinforcing Brand Knowledge: The Case Study of Wanderlust, Local Tourism Agent, Indonesia by Mayasari, Iin & Kertamuda, Fatchiah & Arham, Mochammad & Chris, Handrix. (2019) concluded that the leverage secondary association in the Wanderlust Company has shown strength in the company. This can be seen from the four elements that support it, namely people, places, things, and other brands. These four elements have been optimally carried out by Wanderlust to support the sustainability of his company in order to create equity in his company.

A framework for using co-branding to leverage a brand - L Leuthesser, C Kohli, R Suri - Journal of Brand Management, 2003 – Springer have stated in their study that Successful brands provide quality assurances to consumers and can be leveraged to introduce new products. The most common way of leveraging brands is through line and brand extensions.

Reliance Jio History

Reliance Industries Limited (RIL) is a Fortune 500 company and the biggest private-sector corporation in India. Reliance's products and services portfolio meet approximately all of us on a daily basis, over economic and social bandwidth. The largest company has grown from being a textiles and polyester company to a mingled pro in entertainment, energy, retail, food industry, and digital services.

The inception of Jio was in 2005 when RIL split, the company was known as Infotel Broadband previously, now by this time it is widely acknowledged as "Reliance Jio" (a dream project of Mukesh Ambani). It has begun with broadband services, stepped into 3G and 4G, and is extending its mobile products and services through e-marketing. Mr. Mukesh Ambani had been working on the JIO Infocomm Ltd since 2010.

Reliance Jio Infocomm Limited is an Indian telecommunications company and a subsidiary of Jio Platforms,

headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. It operates a national LTE network with coverage across all 22 telecom circles. It does not offer 2G or 3G service, and instead uses only voice over LTE to provide voice service on its 4G network.

Jio soft launched on 27 December 2015 with a beta for partners and employees and became publicly available on 5 September 2016. As of 31 December 2019, it is the largest mobile network operator in India and the third largest mobile network operator in the world with over 41.08 crore (410.8 million) subscribers.

Jio's Strategy of Leveraging Secondary Brand Associations to Build Brand Equity

1. Reliance, when it introduced Jio it was referred as Reliance Jio. It is so to create association, as consumers are already aware of Reliance Industry.
2. Jio's first ever campaign was launched in the light of giving wings to our Prime Minister Narendra Modi's vision for Digital India. They said, "Jio is a dedication to that Digital India dream of the Prime Minister, his vision for the 1.2 billion people of India."
3. Similarly, other campaigns with slogans like "Now India will fly. Jio is here." Featuring Shahrukh Khan and introducing Jio Prime with a bunch of youngsters singing "Hoyenga hoyenga continue hoyenga" which was to introduce their amazing offers post the unlimited free period.
4. Along with JIO Sim cards, another weapon that was launched by Reliance was LYF (Life) Mobile phones. It was the most affordable 4G LTE Smartphone. So people who couldn't afford high-end smartphones now had all the option at hand. LYF smartphone was endorsed by Kangana Ranaut and other cricket celebrities whereas their "Dhan Dhana Dhan" offer was introduced featuring Deepika Padukone along with other cricket celebrities.

Interpretation:

- Statistics say the firm acquired 50 million subscribers in just 83 days of its launch. And it had about 215 million subscribers by July 2018.
- World record for 16 million subscribers in the first month after launch. Added 7 subscribers per second into the network. Largest optical fiber deployment in the country; 25,000 kms 1st PAN India 4G telecom operator A Digital Disrupter in Indian telecom landscape
- The dominance of the (Jio) brand across the nation is evident from the results from Brand Finance's original market research. Jio scores highest in all metrics – consideration conversion, reputation, recommendation, word of mouth, innovation, customer service and value for money - compared to its telecom competitors in India," it said.
- The brand, it said, has no major weaknesses within the sector, and unlike other telecom brands globally, Jio has shown that it has broken the mould, and enjoys genuine affection from consumers.
- Entering the ranking for the first time this year and claiming the title of the world's 5th strongest brand, is Indian telecom giant, Jio, with a BSI score of 91.7 out of 100 and the elite AAA+ brand strength rating.
- As well as being a standout brand for brand strength, Jio is the fastest-growing brand in the ranking in the telecom sector in terms of brand value, bucking the negative trend across the industry, with a 50% increase to \$4.8 billion.

Conclusion

Reliance Jio has become a biggest & renowned brand in the telecommunication industry. No doubt, there are many

factors which are liable for its grand success such as product strategy, price strategy, place and promotion strategy but one of the very important strategy for its huge success is leveraging of secondary brand association with Jio. From the above case, it is found that the Jio brand is linked to an existing brand that is with its corporate or family brand ie Reliance only. And this Corporate or family brand became a source of much brand equity. Besides the company the country or the geographic locations from which the brand originates also becomes a great source of equity & in the case of Jio it is associated automatically with India. Some Other factors also like association with famous and renowned personality i.e. Mr. Narendra Modi, Shahrukh Khan and Deepika Padukon also became an important determinant in increasing brand equity of Reliance Jio.

References

<https://www.gopromotional.co.uk/blog/what-is-leveraging-secondary-brand-association-to-build-brand-equity/>

<https://www.analyticssteps.com/blogs/reliance-jio-and-jiomart-marketing-strategy-swot-analysis-and-working-ecosystem>

<https://www.exchange4media.com/advertising-news/brand-modileveraging-secondary-brand-associations-58269.html>

<https://brandyuva.in/2018/08/top-reasons-behind-reliance-jio-brand-success.html>

<https://www.thehindu.com/business/Industry/reliance-jio-ranked-fifth-strongest-brand-globally/article33684733.ece>